

AN ITALIAN CIRCULAR ECONOMY MODEL

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ABSTRACT: The study aimed to analyze the economic and environmental sustainability of a case study of an energy power plant that produces electricity from pruning residues of olive groves from nine municipalities in southern Italy. To assess the economic sustainability of the agro-energetic chain, the gross value added (GVA) is calculated. Moreover, the GHG emissions of the agro-energetic pruning supply chain due to both the pruning collection at the field level, and their combustion for energy production at the power plant, are calculated. Moreover, the ecoefficiency ratio was calculated to measure the value added per 1Mg of GHG emitted into the atmosphere. The findings show the whole agro-energetic chain, namely the power plant and the collection company have a good eco-efficiency ratio. In fact, the power plant's ecoefficiency ratio (2.64€ per 1Mg of GHG) is slightly lower than harvest firm one (2.91€ per 1Mg of GHG). The findings could be useful to develop new business models based on the circular economy concept. In fact, the business model proposed could push entrepreneurs towards new income opportunities, at the same time, helping local farms and reducing the environmental impacts.

Keywords: new business model; ecoefficiency ratio; pruning biomass; circular economy.

1 INTRODUCTION

Concerns about emissions from fossil fuel use have stimulated renewable energy adoption, which included bioenergy and its crop residue [1]. Among crop residues, prunings have a significant potential in bioenergy production [2]. In Europe, more than 13 million tons of pruning biomass are yearly available from permanent crops (olive grows, vineyard and orchard); and 80% of them are located in the Mediterranean area, particularly in Italy and Spain [3].

In Italy, it is estimated an annual quantity of pruning biomass over 2.6 Mt comes only from the olive groves [4]. In particular in Apulia Region, are concentrated about 33% of the Italian olive biomass [5].

Although it is an abundant biomass resource, the exploitation of tree prunings for energy purposes is still limited, due mainly to logistics-related constraints [6,7].

On the other hand, the location of bioenergy facilities is profitable in regions where olive groves and vineyards are concentrated, such as in the Mediterranean area [8]. In such conditions, in addition to economic profitability, local network based on agricultural residues could provide social and environmental benefits [9]. Nevertheless, pruning residues are not always considered a valuable resource, but are often a disposal problem [2]. In fact, prunings are usually disposed through open-air burning causing CO₂ emissions [10]; or alternatively, prunings are mulched, causing a threat for transmitting soil disease [11].

In this framework, plants that use tree crop pruning residue for energy purposes could be an interesting solution under economic and environmental point of view.

In Italy, there is only one power plant localized in the southern Italy (Apulia region) that uses exclusively olive pruning residues. This plant of 1 MWe is an interesting case study given its uniqueness at the European level [7,12]. In fact, this plant was chosen as case study in the framework of the AGROinLOG Project (Horizon 2020, Grant Agreement No 727961) aimed at demonstrating the technical, environmental and

economic feasibility of new value chains based on agricultural waste and by-products.

In the literature, there are no studies assessing the economic and environmental sustainability of biomass power plants of 1MWe fueled with pruning residues based on real cases or studies about its ecoefficiency ratio. The ecoefficiency ratio is an useful tool for the firm to achieve greater economic value with lower environmental impacts [13].

Thus, the current study aims to fill this gap by analyzing on the one hand, the economic and environmental sustainability of a case study of power plant (1MWe) that produces energy from olive pruning residues in southern Italy; on the other hand, its ecoefficiency ratio. In fact, to put together the environmental and economic assessment, the ecoefficiency ratio was used to measure the economic value (expressed in value added) per 1 Mg of greenhouse gases emitted into the atmosphere.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

The aim of the work is to analyze the economic and environmental sustainability of a case study of an energy power plant that produces electricity from pruning residues of olive groves from nine municipalities in southern Italy. In particular, the study is focused on the agro-energetic supply chain composed by a small-scale power plant (1 MWe) that produces electricity exclusively from olive tree prunings [14] and a harvest firm that supplies the prunings to the power station collecting them from local farmers. The plant is localized in Apulia region, South Italy, and works in a 10 km radius approximately 7000 hectares of olive groves (75% of the total utilized agricultural area) including nine Apulian municipalities. The total annual amount of prunings potentially is approximately of 25,000–26,000 Mg per year [14], compared to 8000 Mg of biomass annually supplied to the power plant. Moreover, the 1 MWe power plant has an annual operational capacity of 8000 h per year and it provides production of 8000 MWh

annually [14].

To study the economic sustainability of the agro-energetic chain, the gross value added (GVA) is calculated. All economic data come from budgets (years 2016–2017) of both the power plant and the harvest firm.

Moreover, to assess the environmental impact of the agro-energetic chain, the GHG emissions are considered. The emissions into the atmosphere due to the pruning combustion for energy production come from internal data of the power plant, while the GHG emissions due to fuel consumption of the machine harvesters at firm level are estimated using the formula (1) and come from the AGROinLOG project.

In particular, considering an annual comminuted olive pruning biomass of 8000 Mg supplied to the power plant, the CO₂ emission of the pruning harvesting activities carried out by field stage was determined considering a fuel consumption of the machine harvesters of 3.5 L per Mg of comminuted olive pruning (primary data) and an emission of 2.65 kg CO₂ per liter of diesel, according to [15] the following formula:

$$Fe = D * Ec * TP / 1000 \quad (1)$$

where:

Fe = emission of CO₂ due to pruning harvesting and shredding field stage (t CO₂/yield);

D = fuel consumed by the machines per Mg of olive pruning (L/Mg);

Ec = emission of CO₂ per liter of diesel (2.65 Kg CO₂/L);

TP = Total production of comminuted biomass from pruning (Mg/yield).

It is important to underline that the GHG emissions due to olive groves cultivation have not been considered in the study.

Finally, to link the economic and environmental assessment of both the power plant and the harvest firm,

the ecoefficiency method is applied [16,17] and it is expressed as the ratio between economic value and environmental impact of firms. In other words, the ecoefficiency ratio measures the value added of each firm per Mg of GHGs emitted into the atmosphere from both the power plant and harvest firm.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In Table I, emissions in the atmosphere per gross value added (€) produced by the pruning for energy supply chain were analyzed. The higher the ratio value of firm, the higher its economic value per unit of environmental impact.

Table I: Ecoefficiency ratio of the pruning agro-energetic chain in Calimera (LE, Italy).

Ecoefficiency Index	Unit	Value
The power plant		
GVA	€/y	1,237,639
GHG emission	Mg CO ₂ eq/y	469,000
Ecoefficiency ratio	€/Mg CO₂ eq	2.64
The harvest firm		
GVA	€/y	215,659
GHG emission	Mg CO ₂ eq/y	74,000
Ecoefficiency ratio	€/Mg CO₂ eq	2.91

Source: Our elaboration on the firm's data.

The ecoefficiency of each firm making up the energy supply chain analyzed showed that the harvest firm had a better ecoefficiency ratio per unit of GHG emitted into the atmosphere compared to the power plant. In fact, the harvest firm shows a value added of 2.91€ per Mg of greenhouse gases emitted into the atmosphere.

Moreover, the power plant's ecoefficiency ratio is slightly lower than harvest firm one (-9%); in fact, the power plant shows a value added of 2.64€ per Mg of greenhouse gases emitted into the atmosphere. This finding appears to be even more interesting due to the different sectors (industrial and agricultural) that the two firms belong. In fact, contrary to what was expected, the two firms, constituting the energy chain based on olive tree pruning, have shown similar ecoefficiencies.

The findings represent a novelty due to the characteristic of the supply chain, quality of the primary data used, and ecoefficiency evaluation method used. This is due to the novelty of this research that is a combination of economic and environmental aspects never performed before on a real case of a pruning-based biomass power plant. As mentioned above, the biomass plant analyzed is unique in Europe of its kind. Moreover, there is a lack of studies that analyze the ecoefficiency of energy supply chains in the literature. In addition, the economic and environmental parameters used for the ecoefficiency calculation can vary from one study to another [17].

In fact, as mentioned above, the ecoefficiency is a ratio between product or service value and its environmental impact, however, there are numerous ways in which ecoefficiency can be calculated. The authors in [17] provided a set of indicators that cover the broad spectrum of use of products and services, and environmental impacts. The selection of value indicators depends upon the ways in which the ecoefficiency indicators will be used for decision making in firms. For example, firms may want to analyze the ecoefficiency ratio using indicator as profit (or gross value added, etc.) on GHG emissions (or water consumptions etc.). Firms choose indicators that best serve their decision making [17]. Moreover, using an economic indicator divided by the environmental impact provides a useful index to compare within the company throughout time [13]. In our case, following [16]'s study, the gross value added (GVA) (that is the difference between total revenues and costs) and GHG emissions have been chosen to calculate the ecoefficiency ratio. The GVA has been chosen because it is an economic measure of firms and represents the value sufficient to remunerate labor, capital and land in adequate way [18,19]. In the literature, no studies evaluating the ecoefficiency a power plant of 1 MWe (biomass basis), using GVA method, are available and for this reason, the authors believe that this study could fill a knowledge gap in the current literature.

4 CONCLUSION

The study aimed to analyze the economic and environmental sustainability of a case study of an energy power plant that produces electricity from pruning residues of olive groves from nine municipalities in southern Italy. The findings show the whole agro-energetic chain has a good ecoefficiency ratio. In particular, the power plant's ecoefficiency ratio (2.64€ per 1Mg of GHG) is slightly lower than harvest firm one

(2.91€ per 1Mg of GHG). The findings could be useful to develop new business models based on the circular economy concept. In fact, the business model proposed could push entrepreneurs towards new income opportunities, at the same time, helping local farms and reducing the environmental impacts.

5 REFERENCES

- [1] Palmieri, N.; Forleo, M.B.; Giannoccaro, G.; Suardi, A. Environmental impact of cereal straw management: An on-farm assessment. *J. Clean. Prod.* 2017, 142, 2950–2964.
- [2] Picchi, G.; Lombardini, C.; Pari, L.; Spinelli, R. Physical and chemical characteristics of renewable fuel obtained from pruning residues. *J. Clean. Prod.* 2018, 171, 457–463.
- [3] Dyjakon, A.; García-Galindo, D. Implementing agricultural pruning to energy in Europe: Technical, economic and implementation potentials. *Energies* 2019, 12, 1513.
- [4] Pari, L.; Alfano, V.; Garcia-Galindo, D.; Suardi, A.; Santangelo, E. Pruning biomass potential in Italy related to crop characteristics, agricultural practices and agro-climatic conditions. *Energies* 2018, 11, 1365.
- [5] ISTAT. ISTAT Superfici in Produzione—Dati in Complesso 2019; ISTAT: Rome, Italy, 2019.
- [6] Gebresenbet, G.; Bosona, T.; Olsson, S.O.; Garcia, D. Smart system for the optimization of logistics performance of the pruning biomass value chain. *Appl. Sci.* 2018, 8, 1162.
- [7] Pari, L.; Suardi, A.; Santangelo, E.; García-Galindo, D.; Scarfone, A.; Alfano, V. Current and innovative technologies for pruning harvesting: A review. *Biomass Bioenergy* 2017, 107, 398–410.
- [8] Delivand, M.K.; Cammerino, A.R.B.; Garofalo, P.; Monteleone, M. Optimal locations of bioenergy facilities, biomass spatial availability, logistics costs and GHG (greenhouse gas) emissions: A case study on electricity productions in South Italy. *J. Clean. Prod.* 2015, 99, 129–139.
- [9] Bosona, T.; Gebresenbet, G. Evaluating Logistics Performances of Agricultural Prunings for Energy Production: A Logistics Audit Analysis Approach. *Logistics* 2018, 2, 19.
- [10] Gonçalves, C.; Evtuyugina, M.; Alves, C.; Monteiro, C.; Pio, C.; Tomé, M. Organic particulate emissions from field burning of garden and agriculture residues. *Atmos. Res.* 2011, 101, 666–680.
- [11] Repullo, M.A.; Carbonell, R.; Hidalgo, J.; Rodríguez-Lizana, A.; Ordóñez, R. Using olive pruning residues to cover soil and improve fertility. *Soil Tillage Res.* 2012, 124, 36–46.
- [12] Dario, A. L'ulivo del Salento per il primo impianto a biomasse d'Europa. sole 24 ore, 18 February 2010.
- [13] Ichimura, M.; Nam, S.; Bonjour, S.; Rankine, H.; Carisma, B.; Qiu, Y.; Khrueachotikul, R. Eco-Efficiency Indicators: Measuring Resource-Use Efficiency and the Impact of Economic Activities on the Environment; Greening of Economic Growth Series; ESCAP: Bangkok, Thailand, 2009; Volume 25.
- [14] CERTH. Ufg, C. and D6.3: Flagship Success Cases Update v1; CERTH: Thessaloniki, Greece, 2017.
- [15] Ministry for the Environment. Summary of Emissions Factors for the Guidance for Voluntary Corporate Greenhouse Gas Reporting—2015; Ministry for the Environment: Wellington, New Zealand, 2015.
- [16] Forleo, M.B.; Palmieri, N.; Suardi, A.; Coaloa, D.; Pari, L. The eco-efficiency of rapeseed and sunflower cultivation in Italy. Joining environmental and economic assessment. *J. Clean. Prod.* 2018, 172, 3138–3153.
- [17] Verfaillie, H.; Bidwell, R. Measuring Eco-Efficiency—A Guide to Reporting Company Performance; World Business Council for Sustainable Development: Conch, Geneva, 2001.
- [18] Lozano, F.J.; Lozano, R. Assessing the potential sustainability benefits of agricultural residues: Biomass conversion to syngas for energy generation or to chemicals production. *J. Clean. Prod.* 2018, 172, 4162–4169.
- [19] Thomassen, M.A.; Dolman, M.A.; van Calker, K.J.; de Boer, I.J.M. Relating life cycle assessment indicators to gross value added for Dutch dairy farms. *Ecol. Econ.* 2009, 68, 2278–2284.

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7 LOGO SPACE

